

**DEVELOPMENT OF HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION OF A DEVICE FOR
REMOTE MONITORING OF HEALTH INDICATORS USING GPS -SYSTEM**

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Abstract. *In this paper, some indicators of human health are considered. An analysis of hardware platforms for the implementation of a device for remote monitoring of health indicators was carried out. A variant of hardware implementation of a remote monitoring device is proposed. The device allows you to monitor body temperature and heart rate in real time and send the coordinates of the controlled object in case of emergency.*

Keywords: *Health indicators, hardware platform, GSM, GPS, temperature sensor, heart rate sensor.*

Vital indicators of human health include: blood pressure; body temperature; breathing rate; heart rate, saturation [1].

Body temperature. Normal body temperature does not change significantly with age. However, with age, the body finds it more difficult to maintain a normal temperature at a constant level, especially when fat loss occurs. For this reason, older people note chilliness. With age, the ability to sweat decreases. Therefore, older patients are at higher risk of overheating and heat stroke. In old age, the risk of hypothermia is also increased. Fever in diseases in the elderly is a more alarming sign compared to young people.

Respiration and pulse rate. In old age, the ability to endure heavy physical exertion decreases. The body needs more time to increase heart rate during exercise, return the pulse to normal after exercise. Although lung function declines with age, respiratory rate remains virtually unchanged.

All healthy adults at rest have a respiratory rate of 16 per minute. The pulse rate is 78 beats per minute. Human heart rate varies at different ages. So, at 40-50 years old, the norm is 65-90 beats per minute, in people over 51 years old - 60-90 beats per minute.

Blood pressure. The pressure fluctuates within 120/80. Elderly people report dizziness when changing body position to vertical. This is due to a decrease in blood pressure (orthostatic hypotension).

Other pressure problems associated with age:

- increased blood pressure (hypertension);
- slow heart rate (bradycardia);
- Irregular heart rhythm (arrhythmia).

Saturation. Saturation is a measure of oxygen saturation in the blood. The saturation rate for a healthy person is considered when 95% or more of hemoglobin is associated with oxygen. This is saturation - the percentage of oxyhemoglobin in the blood [1].

There are many multifunctional debugging platforms used in the development of applications for microcontrollers and embedded computers. Consider the most popular among them: Raspberry Pi and Arduino. Let's compare the technical characteristics, and also figure out which solution is better to use for a particular project. Externally, the two boards are very similar, but these are devices of different classes and each has its own characteristics.

Arduino [2] . The board has an AVR microcontroller from Atmel (different models), there is a power input, as well as a set of input-output contacts (Fig.1). Arduino is not a full-fledged computer - in fact, it is a microcontroller with some peripherals for normal operation: a power stabilizer, a quartz resonator, reset circuits, etc. There is no operating system (embedded or general purpose), and the code is created using the development environment of the same name and is uploaded to the microcontroller using a special bootloader via RS-232, USB or Ethernet interfaces , depending on the composition of the board's periphery.

Fig.1. The appearance of the Arduino board

The device simplifies the work with electronics for artists, designers, schoolchildren and students, Internet of Things (IoT) and robotics enthusiasts, as well as anyone interested in creating interactive objects or environments. You need to program the microcontroller in the Arduino IDE in C / C ++, but alternative options are available, since the platform is completely open (including the hardware). You can use professional packages like Eclipse or Microsoft Visual Studio , as well as simpler software, like the Scratch visual environment for Arduino .

The main function of the Arduino board is to interact with gadgets and sensors. It is great for solving the problems of testing equipment prototypes, allowing you to go beyond the virtual world to interact with the physical environment. Arduino- based designs can receive information through sensors, as well as control various actuators. For example, do-it-yourselfers actively use them in smart home solutions or in simple robots.

Arduino family has models of different configurations: Uno , Nano , Micro , DUE, MKR and others. Some are even equipped with ARM controllers. An interesting feature of the platform is the ability to connect the so-called. shields (expansion boards) to support Bluetooth , Ethernet , GPRS, various sensors and much more. The features are cumulative so you can add multiple shields to one board, and they eliminate the hassle of extra wiring: the boards are designed to mount via pin headers. The housing and mounting structure are not provided - you need to take care of them yourself.

Since the hardware is also open, there are many compatible clones in addition to the original products under the Arduino brand . In general, this is an excellent constructor for experiments, various tasks that do not require high computing power.

Raspberry Pi [3]. In 2012, the British Raspberry Foundation Pi launched a series of compact single-board computers to promote the teaching of basic computer science in schools in developing countries. Since then, developers around the world have been using Raspberry Pi for

education, prototyping , automation, and other tasks in the industrial and telecommunications industry.

Unlike Arduino , Raspberry Pi is a full-fledged computer with an ARM microprocessor (Fig.2). Bigger than a simple MCU: 1GB, 2GB or 4GB LPDDR4 SDRAM, video output, 2x mini HDMI, SD card port, audio port , CSI camera port, DSI display port, 2x USB 2.0 and 2x USB 3.0 ports Raspberry Pi 4. Gigabit available Ethernet , Wi-Fi , Bluetooth 4.2 and input / output pins (GPIO). A series of universal I/O contacts allows the Malinka to control the electronic components of physical computers and easily integrate into IoT solutions . The board usually ships with the Linux operating system preinstalled .

Fig.2. The appearance of the Raspberry board Pi

Since this is already a computer with a rather complex OS (embedded or general purpose), a power failure can cause damage to software and installed applications (Arduino does not have this problem). Raspberry The Pi needs to be shut down properly, just like larger machines. Most models of these mini-computers come completely assembled on a palm-sized printed circuit board: in addition to the board itself, the case and power supply are included, and the memory card must be ordered separately.

Espressif ESP8266 and ESP32 [4] . Adding Wi-Fi to a project used to be quite an expensive proposition. Espressif Systems introduced the ESP8266 with modules selling for as little as \$3. This chip was so valuable that an open source community quickly formed around the chip. Over the course of two years, the support has been quite significant, even using the Arduino IDE. Since then, the company has also released the ESP32 with a more powerful processor and support for both WiFi and Bluetooth (Fig.3).

The ESP8266 and ESP32 both ship with Xtensa cores and run the FreeRTOS real-time operating system with platforms offering a cross between power consumption, real-time capabilities of Arduino boards, and the full featured nature of Raspberry Pi Linux SBC.

Fig.3. Appearance of ESP32 boards

Below is a comparison of ESP32 with ESP8266:

- WiFi speed varies up to 72.2 Mbps for ESP8266 and up to 150 Mbps for ESP32;
- Bluetooth compatible unlike ESP8266;
- ESP32 has 12-bit SAR and two 8-bit DAC channels compared to ESP8266's 10-bit SAR;
- While the ESP32 has eight channels, the ESP8266 operates on a single channel;
- The ESP32 has multiple sensors, including an eight-channel touch sensor, as well as a temperature sensor and a Hall effect sensor, while the ESP8266 has no built-in sensors.

The ESP8266 and ESP32 are designed for use in the wearable electronics, IoT industry , and mobile devices, and you'll find plenty of well-documented designs based on any of these materials online.

Each option has its own advantages. If you need decent computing power and multimedia capabilities, you should choose Raspberry Pi . You can even make a full-fledged desktop computer with Linux and a graphical interface out of it. If serious resources are not required, the Arduino or one of the third-party clone boards is ideal . Programming a microcontroller is much easier given the many alternative development environments available. Analog sensors are easier to connect to the Arduino , so if you only need simple processing of data based on readings from secondary devices and relatively uncomplicated interaction between parts of the device, this is an excellent option.

When you need to add Wi-Fi or Bluetooth connectivity to your project, the ESP8266 or ESP32 boards are the obvious and cost-effective choice.

Arduino platform was developed (Fig.4).

The device incorporates a microcontroller system (Arduino), a GSM module, a GPS module, heart rate and body temperature sensors, and a rechargeable battery [5, 6] .

The device allows you to perform the following functions:

- remote monitoring of body temperature;
- remote heart rate monitoring;
- determination and transmission of the coordinates of the controlled object;
- sending information at critical values of temperature and pulse.

Fig.4. Remote health monitoring device

The GSM -module is used to organize the transmission of data and SMS -messages on the state of health indicators. The GPS -module allows you to determine the coordinates of the monitoring object.

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